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List of abbreviations

EU	European Union
R&I	Research & innovation
STEM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics

Executive summary

This report describes the **approach of an in-project training methodology and its plan for the RE4GREEN project to develop gender-specific capacities and skills of RE4GREEN consortium partners and their staff for use in the various tasks during the project.** Firstly, RE4GREEN's gender-responsive methodology is presented. Following this, the findings from an internal survey, aiming to identify the capacity-building needs of consortium partners, are detailed. In addition, this section will elaborate on how these findings will shape the development of RE4GREEN's comprehensive framework for research and innovation (R&I) to address environmental and climate ethics and integrity challenges. Subsequently, the **planned outputs intended to bolster the consortium's capacity to conduct gender-responsive and inclusive research**, including training sessions, a checklist, a gender glossary, and factsheets, are outlined.

Whilst this report frames RE4GREEN's bold stance, which centres gender considerations in the promotion of a just and inclusive Green Transition, **the methodology and plan presented herein may offer a blueprint for similar projects.**

Introduction

Our world is increasingly affected by global climate and environmental events. Research and innovation (R&I) is poised to mitigate these pressing challenges. The European Green Deal, for example, emphasises the promotion of technology and sustainable solutions. However, R&I may entail risks for individuals, communities, and the environment.

RE4GREEN aims to provide a framework for R&I – including training, guidelines, and policy recommendations – that comprehensively accounts for environmental and climate ethics to support the transition to a sustainable economy and society. This framework will be rooted in a bottom-up methodology which employs Social Labs: participatory platforms that bring together diverse stakeholders to address complex social challenges over an extended period. However, for this framework to be truly effective, it must be inclusive.

Gender inequality and environmental issues intersect. As such, this report contends that **initiatives advancing the Green Transition must take a bold approach concerning gender aspects.** Such projects may consider a comprehensive training programme to foster discussions and enhance understanding of gender and inclusivity.

Drawing from an internal survey conducted within the RE4GREEN consortium, revealing diverse perspectives on gender and the European Green Transition, feminist approaches, and workplace policies, this report delineates a methodology, plan, and timeline to advance a gender-responsive approach within the project. This includes developing **training sessions, generating factsheets, compiling a gender glossary, and formulating a checklist.** Crucially, the insights gleaned from the internal survey and the plan presented herein could offer a roadmap for similar projects seeking to enhance gender inclusivity and awareness to promote a just and inclusive transition.

Gender training methodology

RE4GREEN's gender-responsive work will consider an **ecofeminist approach which views the main causes of the climate crisis as the intersecting systems of colonialism, patriarchy, and capitalism**. This approach, created by Women Engage for a Common Future (WECF), may be summarised as follows:

Ecofeminism emerged as a concept during the second-wave feminist movement of the 1970s. The phrase 'ecological feminism' was first used by Françoise d'Eaubonne in 1972, although since then the concept has been considered in different contexts and subsequently expanded upon. Rosemary Radford wrote in 1975 that there is no liberation for women and no solution to the ecological crisis within a society [whose] fundamental mode of operation is domination. By highlighting the Self–Other relationship, in which the 'self' dominates and oppresses the 'other,' ecofeminism unpacks the binary self-other categories that underpin Western philosophy, colonialism and patriarchy. For example: 'man' – 'woman', 'straight' – 'queer', 'white' – 'non-white'. The oppressed 'other' is bound by the same structures and institutions that have fuelled ecological destruction and the climate crisis. Ecofeminism argues that the climate crisis and oppression of marginalised groups are intertwined, and that neither issue can be solved independently. (Stock and Heffernan, 2021)

Whilst some aspects of the RE4GREEN project focus on women, such as ensuring a 45% or higher participation rate of women in all project activities, RE4GREEN's approach to feminist capacity building moves beyond women as an object of analysis. RE4GREEN will **consider how structures of oppression could manifest in research endeavours and provide tools to dismantle these structures effectively**.

Capacity-building needs

WECF prepared an internal **survey** circulated among RE4GREEN partners ($n=22$) to understand the **diversity of experiences and knowledge within the consortium**. Understanding the situated positionality of the project partners is important to unpack the unique ways systems of oppression will manifest in forms of discrimination and privilege in research activities. This co-creation approach to capacity building is grounded in the belief that **meaningful and sustainable change requires active engagement and collaboration among all partners involved in research**.

Firstly, the survey contained questions to ascertain the partners' knowledge of gender, feminism, and the Green Transition. Partners were also asked about their organisational structure as it relates to gender issues and, finally, about what they expected from the project's capacity-building initiatives. All questions, as depicted in the following graphs, were formulated as Likert scale statements, ranging from 1 for "strongly disagree" to 5 for "strongly agree." Additionally, partners were provided with open-ended fields to further elaborate on their answers.

Gender and the European Green Transition

Partners largely agreed that understanding gender roles was key to a just transition, with some emphasising that **women and gender non-conforming people should not be left behind to achieve a just transition**. Respondents who selected “neither agree nor disagree” often cited either a lack of familiarity with gender roles or the belief that gender is not the primary consideration for a fair transition. The RE4GREEN project, supported by gender-responsive training sessions, will build on this finding to show the **centrality of gender within a just transition whilst highlighting that feminist approaches are not mutually exclusive**.

Figure 1 – Opinions on gender and the Green Deal

Additional survey questions asked RE4GREEN partners to pinpoint **structural barriers to both environmental justice and gender equality in their countries**. Most partners identified socio-economic barriers, e.g., unequal parental leave, the gender wage gap, sexist employment practices, and the burden of care responsibilities. Additionally, respondents noted that emission-producing practices, such as transport, agriculture, and the challenges of entrenched cultural practices or lifestyle choices, represent key barriers to achieving environmental justice. Efforts to build an ethics and integrity framework for R&I to support the Green Transition should take these barriers into account. Accordingly, the RE4GREEN gender training sessions will focus on addressing these socio-economic and environmental challenges to ensure a comprehensive approach to promoting environmental justice and gender equality.

In the broader context of research on environmental ethics, it is imperative to move beyond conventional economic and environmental frameworks. RE4GREEN, supported by the gender training sessions, will build on an analysis of the structural effects of capitalism to **incorporate feminist perspectives that address other hindrances to the Green Transition, notably coloniality.**

Coloniality encompasses the continuation of colonial power structures and violence, necessitating the adoption of anti-colonial approaches aimed at dismantling such structures (Lugones, 2010). Understanding coloniality is vital for grasping the relationship between the EU, capitalism, and the Green Transition. This is because many European countries, historically established as colonial powers (referred to as the “core”), continue to extract wealth and resources from lower-resource contexts (referred to as the “periphery”). This not only contributes to the climate crisis but also hinders periphery countries from tackling the effects of the climate crisis themselves. These asymmetrical power structures continue in the EU’s relations with its external partners today (Crochet, 2022; Dunlap and Riquito, 2023). Given that activities aiming to support the Green Transition often involve epistemological production from core countries, it is vital to **recognise and mitigate the reproduction of these colonial dynamics** within such endeavours. In this context, the RE4GREEN gender training sessions will aim to provide partners with the necessary tools and insights to effectively mitigate these dynamics and promote equitable participation.

Feminist approaches

The RE4GREEN internal survey revealed varying conceptions of feminism, with some listing types of feminism and others expressing their uncertainty around this question. **Feminism consists of diverse perspectives**, such as intersectionality, which acknowledges the interconnected nature of social identities and strives to address multiple forms of oppression simultaneously, and ecofeminism, which examines the interrelation between gender inequality and environmental degradation. Thus, RE4GREEN, supported by the gender training materials, will leverage multiple feminist frameworks to ensure the generation of nuanced insights and effective strategies for developing a comprehensive R&I framework promoting a just transition.

Many survey respondents challenged the concept of the gender binary as well as the idea that feminism exclusively concerns women. In activities supporting the Green Transition, gender itself is a concept based on the construction of systems of difference, and the assumed naturalness of pairing certain genders with certain bodies needs to be deconstructed. Those who do not conform to the traditional gender categories of “men” and “women” often experience additional oppression because these categories originated from Western perspectives and were reinforced during colonial times. This entails unequal treatment, exclusion, and limited access to resources due to societal norms and expectations tied to binary gender roles. **Unveiling the socially constructed nature of gender is an important factor in achieving a just transition – supporting inclusivity, systemic equality, and the efficacy of R&I solutions.**

Figure 2 – Understanding of feminism

Thus, while ecofeminism initially embraced a binary framework, **RE4GREEN will implement a non-binary approach**, moving away from an essentialist discourse. RE4GREEN will reflect on masculinities, femininities, and the associated terminology regarding sex and gender in its work.

Workplace policies

A just transition also necessitates gender-responsive policies within the workplaces of those involved in Green Transition initiatives. Thus, the internal survey queried partners about workplace plans and policies related to gender. Recruitment policies, sexual harassment policies, and gender equality plans were the most common types of gender policies, although only half of all partners answering the questionnaire said they had such policies in their workplace. In addition, some were not aware of the content of the gender equality policies in their workplace.

Figure 3 – Organisational gender policies

The adequacy of gender-related policies also varied among respondents, revealing inconsistencies in workplace standards. Additionally, when asked about structural barriers to gender equality in the workplace, respondents shared personal experiences reflecting patriarchal workplace cultures. Conversely, some participants believed their workplaces were free from such barriers. **These findings point to the importance of raising awareness about gender policies and providing necessary tools in the workplace to advance gender equality.** RE4GREEN gender training materials will therefore encourage partners to reflect on the invisible dynamics that may be present in their workplace and how these manifest in different contexts. This will cultivate a **gender-transformative environment within the consortium, creating a ripple effect with positive changes in respective partner organisations.**

Figure 4 – Adequacy of gender policies

Outputs

The preceding section revealed key dynamics concerning gender, the Green Transition, feminism, and workplace practices and policies, highlighting how the training materials will address the identified gaps. The following section will further describe the materials to be developed, including **training for partners on facilitating gender-responsive, bottom-up participatory research using the Social Lab methodology, factsheets to inform RE4GREEN's ethics and integrity framework for R&I in the Green Transition, a gender glossary to ensure a shared understanding of essential terms, and checklists to enhance gender responsiveness and inclusivity**. These resources could prove valuable for other initiatives promoting a gender-responsive approach to the Green Transition.

The materials described herein will be developed in **co-creation with project partners** and will evolve according to their needs as well as project findings. To accommodate sufficient feedback from partners following the initial training sessions, the content of the final two training sessions remains undefined.

Social Labs

The RE4GREEN project is rooted in a bottom-up approach using the Social Lab methodology to reflect diverse stakeholder perspectives. Social Labs involve engagement on complex social issues with diverse stakeholders over an extended period (Hassan, 2014; Timmermans et al., 2020).

As a participatory methodology generating rich insights through activities like interviews, group discussions, and workshops, Social Labs should be facilitated in a gender-responsive and inclusive manner. This ensures that the insights gathered are representative of diverse perspectives, contributing to more holistic and effective solutions for the Green Transition. In RE4GREEN, the facilitation of the Social Labs will be rooted in an intersectional ecofeminist approach and will utilise a feminist moderation tool to foster discussions that embrace inclusivity.

By utilising an intersectional ecofeminist approach, RE4GREEN partners will gain an understanding of how structural inequalities can manifest in the planning and facilitation of the Social Labs and how best to address them. Intersectionality was coined by legal scholar Crenshaw (1989), who argued that recognising where experiences of sexism and racism intersect is vital to challenging them as systems of oppression. Since its inception, the concept has been expanded to examine how a **wider range of identities intersect to inform lived realities**.

Intersectionality is a constitutive element of mainstream feminism, as it allows for the unpacking of multiple layers of oppression (Taylor, 2011; Davis, 2008). However, the uplifting of intersectionality from specific Black feminist contexts and into academia has led to its commodification and weakening, where it is sometimes used merely to list different identities without addressing the structures underpinning them (Fine, 2009, in Guidroz and Berger, 2009, p. 70). Therefore, **gender-responsive training sessions will encompass understanding how multiple co-constitutive identities and experiences can be effectively integrated into the Social Labs**.

Individuals may exhibit subtle behaviours or make remarks that convey derogatory or discriminatory messages toward others based on their perceived characteristics. **These actions, known as microaggressions or master suppression techniques, will be addressed in the RE4GREEN training sessions on Social Lab facilitation, drawing on WECF's recent development of a tool on feminist moderation techniques.** This will include how to challenge such master suppression techniques, ensuring equitable participation, and address conflict inclusively and safely. In such situations, employing feminist techniques for de-escalation and avoiding polarisation can help address power imbalances that may arise during discussions.

Regarding recruitment, **diversity among participants is vital**. This goes further than just utilising a tick box exercise of different identity characteristics. Training in this regard will focus on factors to consider when mapping stakeholders, including hard-to-reach groups and barriers to participation. Creating a safe and accessible space – including the establishment of guidelines for respectful communication, accommodation of participants' diverse needs, and promotion of openness – is also of importance here, as this will allow for a Social Lab environment in which diverse perspectives can be shared freely.

Regarding the specific objectives of the social labs, in order to be able to build a community for sustained bottom-up engagement, awareness raising, and exchange across stakeholders, a feminist approach is vital. Our training will allow partners leading social labs to be able to reevaluate how stakeholders may hold differing opinions related to their positionality.

As the subsequent two objectives on focus on bottom-up input and co-development of guidelines and recommendations, WECF will also utilise its experience in engaging a wider variety of stakeholders in recommendation processes. It is important to know recommendations may come in various forms depending on the experiences of the stakeholders involved, and these need to be formulated using accessible language.

Factsheets, gender glossary, and checklist

Figure 5 – Factsheet topics

Since factsheets provide concise and factual information about various gender-and-climate-related topics, issues, or initiatives, they serve as valuable educational resources, helping individuals and organisations grasp complex issues in easily understandable formats. Also, factsheets on gender and climate, research ethics, and technology offer crucial data, statistics, and research findings that may serve as the foundation for **evidence-based advocacy, policymaking, and decision-making processes**.

Gender glossaries are important tools to define and clarify key terms, concepts, and terminology related to structures of oppression. RE4GREEN will thus develop a glossary encompassing terms related to gender and inclusivity within the context of the Green Transition. This will ensure clear communication and understanding across diverse partners and audiences, promote inclusivity within project activities by providing a common language and terminology, reduce misunderstandings, and foster respectful dialogue. Gender glossaries are

particularly valuable in contexts where gender-related terms may be complex, nuanced, or evolving, such as discussions around gender diversity, intersectionality, and LGBTQ+. By incorporating inclusive terminology, the RE4GREEN consortium can actively contribute to shaping discussions within the policy spheres relevant to its work.

Projects committed to promoting gender-responsive approaches in the Green Transition should ensure that all their outputs are aligned with principles of gender responsiveness and inclusivity. In this regard, a **checklist can offer partners a structured framework to evaluate their training, guidelines, and policy recommendations**, pinpointing any instances of gender bias or discrimination and proposing actionable measures to rectify them.

Overview and Structure of outputs

Table 1 highlights the outputs supporting a gender-transformative approach within the RE4GREEN project. As described above, these include **online training sessions, a gender glossary, a checklist, and factsheets**. These outputs will be collaboratively developed with partners, each building upon the others to address emerging feedback, insights, and challenges.

Outputs	Deadline
Online Training 1: Ecofeminist approaches to the climate crisis and recruitment techniques	M6
Glossary	M12
Online Training 2: Q & A session for Social Lab leaders on the Feminist Moderation Tool	M12
Factsheet: Gender and climate	M12
Checklist	M12
Online Training 3: Feminist approaches to research	M16
Factsheet: Gender and STEM	M16
Online Training 4: Gender and STEM	M24
Online Training 5: To be decided	M30
Online Training 6: To be decided	M36

Table 1 – Capacity-building outputs

Structure of Outputs

Online training sessions

Will each be 90 minutes long and will reflect on the survey findings presented herein and the experiences of the project partners, using a **highly interactive approach (incorporating online tools such as Zoom and Mentimeter) to ensure meaningful participation**. Training sessions will link the individual experiences of partners with wider structures relevant to the project such as patriarchy, colonialism, and capitalism.

Trainings will change depending on the context, but overall they will contain the following key elements:

- Ice breaker/check in to see who is in the room and how they are feeling about the training
- Knowledge transfer using powerpoint presentation
- Breakout rooms for group discussions to reflect on information with guiding questions – encouraging participants to bring in their own personal examples of the topic
- Group activities in the plenary on interactive software such as ideaboardz, miroboard

Online Training 1: Ecofeminist approaches to the climate crisis: There was a keen interest in understanding ecofeminism from the partners; as such, this will form the basis of the first training session. Whilst the first training session will highlight some of the tools that this feminist lens provides when analysing climate issues from an intersectional perspective, the second training will encompass a feminist approach to research ethics, including reflections on positionality and the coloniality of epistemological production.

Online Training 2: Q & A session for Social Lab leaders on the Feminist Moderation Tool: Partners will be given WECF's feminist moderation tool and be asked to work through it in their own time, before coming to a Q and A session where they will work together with WECF on any questions the partners might have relating to the social labs. Additionally, how to relate the work within the tool to the contexts of the social labs will be covered.

Online Training 3: Feminist approaches to research: This training will centre the decolonial feminist reflections on the coloniality of knowledge production. Partners will be encouraged to reflect on the epistemological positioning of their organisations and the project itself, how we relate to those we extract knowledge from and how this will be used within the context of an EU funded project.

Online Training 4: Gender and STEM: WECF will present existing data alongside the factsheet (European Green Deal and STEM jobs); reasons for low representation for women in STEM (pay and care gap; working environment; etc.); good practices; challenges. A tentative plan (which may encompass a separate training depending on needs of partners) will be to reflect on "technology" as a concept itself, unpacking gendered conceptions of technology.

Glossary

WECF will build off its previous gender glossaries which explain key terms that will be used throughout the capacity building (e.g., patriarchy, colonialism, intersectionality). The glossary will also contain a table which outlines preferred language e.g., using “racialised groups” instead of “race”. The aim of the glossary is to ensure our deliverables have the most progressive language and that partners are on the same page regarding language.

Factsheets

Factsheets will be used by partners as a starting point for discussion in online trainings so they are aware of some of the basic concepts and state of the art related to key topics. These will be explained in plain english alongside key concepts and recommendations for further reading.

Conclusion

The methodology and plan set out in this report will form the basis for RE4GREEN's gender-responsive approach, emphasising its commitment to promoting a just and inclusive Green Transition. The training sessions, checklist, factsheets, and gender glossary, developed in co-creation with project partners, will not only bolster the consortium's capacity for gender-responsive and inclusive research practices but will also serve as a model for similar initiatives.

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